

Emotional Intelligence in Leadership

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Abstract:- In contrast to the more conventional domains of specific knowledge, general intelligence, and technical or professional skills, emotional intelligence is a set of qualities and competencies that encompasses a wide range of individual skills and dispositions, commonly referred to as soft skills or inter and intra-personal skills. Our biological constitution includes emotions, which accompany us to work every day and have an impact on our conduct. Knowing one's feelings, controlling emotions, inspiring oneself, recognizing emotions in others, and managing relationships are the five components of emotional intelligence. The subject of emotional intelligence has received a lot of research. The goal of the current study is to comprehend leaders' emotional intelligence. This study employs qualitative research method, more precisely – textual analysis. Concepts of emotional intelligence, leadership, psychology of leadership, resonant and dissonant leaders are being examined in this study.

Keywords:- Resonant and Dissonant Leaders, Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence, IQ, EQ, Leadership

I. INTRODUCTION

Society knows different forms of intelligence (mathematical, verbal, kinesthetic, and many other types), but the most important for interpersonal relationships is the emotional one. Emotional intelligence enables a person to recognize and accept his own and other people's emotions and to identify their causes. Those emotionally intelligent people can approach a particular problem from a different point of view and develop their creative side faster. Also, emotional intelligence enables easier social integration into society.

Both in private life and business, social relationships are the solution to healthy and stable communication. Building a good relationship with his subordinates helps the leader in performing tasks that are aimed directly at achieving the organization's goals. For employees to be as productive as possible in the workplace, a friendly atmosphere should be created, which still implies the authority of the leader.

Human resources in business can be improved, along with certain profiles of employees, by the active work of leaders on their qualities and skills. Developing emotional intelligence in work leads to knowledge that enables the maintenance of a stable working atmosphere in the service of better business operations of the organization.

With high levels of various types of intelligence, emphasizing desirable and reducing negative traits, and continuous work aimed at developing the skills needed in the job, a leader is built that employees are happy to follow. As a person who manages various processes in the organization, the leader should be representative and stable.

Taking into account that management and leadership are often mentioned as synonyms, the basic differences between managers and leaders are listed and the concept of leadership in today's business is explained in more detail. It is desirable that every leader is emotionally intelligent, and that he is a good and stable leader who would lead the institution towards the given goal.

II. THE IMPORTANCE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE FOR LEADERSHIP

Leadership skills can only be developed if one participates in discussions and reflections and has a desire for experience. Empathy allows leaders to feel the emotions of another person or group even when no one says anything. The characteristics necessary for the successful work of a leader are communication skills, adaptability, self-control, motivation to work, effectiveness in a group, effectiveness in organizing, the potential for leadership, as well as adequate intellectual functioning, expertise, and experience. Leaders ask questions and try new things just to see what happens. Such leaders are able to learn information that will help them make decisions more successfully. Until recently, the prevailing belief was that the business world was devoid of emotions. The rules in the business world are changing and our abilities are now being assessed by new measures: it is no longer just how smart we are or how professional we are, but also how well we manage ourselves and successfully achieve relationships with other people. Emotional intelligence (EI or EQ) is the ability to recognize, understand and manage one's own and other people's emotions. This term focuses on the role of feelings in our daily lives, how they affect our reason and behavior and how we can use them to our advantage. Today, science tells us that emotions are not opposed to rationality, but that they are part of it. Intellect is powerful, but it is impersonal, it can only serve, and emotions are the ones that lead.

III. PSYCHOLOGY OF LEADERSHIP

When we talk about a leader, then it is possible to determine that how he realizes his leadership position depends to a significant extent on his very personality, his character, and intelligence, both concerning himself, his followers, and colleagues, and also to different dimensions of the situations with which is facing. In addition to the mentioned dimensions, the leader is also determined by his temperament and his abilities. Temperament implies the emotional way of reacting to individuals, in different situations, which implies speed, strength, and the duration of human activities. Abilities speak about the degree of success of a person in performing various jobs.

Human abilities include intelligence (ability to cope with new circumstances), psychomotor abilities (dexterity), and sensory abilities (sight, hearing, smell, etc.). When we talk about a person's character, we mean his voluntary qualities: persistence, determination, consistency in behavior, initiative, etc., and from a moral point of view, a character refers to honesty, selfishness, modesty, stinginess, etc. Therefore, we can say that under character traits we mean the characteristics of an individual that show his willful qualities and his attitude towards the moral principles that apply to society.

There are also somewhat more comprehensive understandings of character, which in the concept of character recognize the essential values of a person. Thus, even in the ancient period, the Greek philosopher Heraclitus claimed that nothing in this world defines a person as important as his character - neither knowledge, nor strength, nor beauty, nor disposition. , neither property nor any other circumstances. In contemporary conditions, different states and military traditions and cultures give unequal importance to the character and its influence on leadership, in different means and conditions. The importance given to character within Anglo-American theory and practice is noticeable. In the majority of all these understandings and definitions, the character should be recognized as a determinant that significantly distinguishes the qualities of a personality. Thus, within the framework of leadership theory in the US Army, character is defined as the sum total of an individual's personal qualities, and as the connection between personal values and the behavior of that person".

Within the analysis of Churchill's Art of Leadership, it is contrasted that there are four essential elements that are found in each of the historical leaders. They are character, instinct, imagination, and will. Although the character is emphasized as one of the most important elements of Churchill's personality, within the same analysis, 4 traits of Churchill's leadership ability are highlighted, which directly illustrate his character: openness and simplicity of expression, decisiveness, the ability to balance care for details with observing a wider window, and historical imagination that shaped its borrowing. This understanding of character is understood as a combination of personality traits that produce behavior in accordance with personal values, regardless of circumstances. Speaking about this,

Churchill says: "Health, intelligence, and shrewdness were bad for Hitler because those qualities enabled him to serve evil purposes.

That's why questions of leadership are ultimately only questions of character. Leadership is not primarily a question of intellect- judgments are more often dominated by moral than intellectual content. Character, therefore, in a general sense, is understood and understood in the context of the defining characteristics of man.

IV. INTELLIGENCE – DEFINITION IN PSYCHOLOGY AND LEADERSHIP

Although psychological science knows several concepts about which it is difficult to reach a complete consensus, in terms of their unique understanding and definition, certainly intelligence is a concept about the understanding, definition, and interpretation of which there are more polemics than about any other concept. Most psychologists, however, agree that intelligence is more of a potential than an innate or fully developed ability, which is very significant from a leadership perspective. Therefore, from a leadership perspective, it is important to perceive intelligence as a combination of innate characteristics of the nervous system and developmental intelligence, shaped by experience and learning. From a large number of existing definitions of intelligence, we will include in this analysis the one that emphasizes: "intelligence is a mental characteristic that consists of the ability to learn from experience, adapting to new situations, understanding and using abstract concepts and using knowledge to navigate the environment". Within this consideration, it is possible to add another definition of intelligence: "Intelligence is defined as the overall efficiency of a person in thought-driven activities". In the analysis of the content, structure, and factors of intelligence, there is also no single approach and common starting point within the framework of psychological science.

In 1938, in these so-called factor techniques, the American psychologist Louis Thurston came up with seven primary factors of intelligence, which we define as follows: S - spatial (spatial) ability, P - perceptive factor, N - numerical factor, V - verbal factor, M – memory, i.e. memory factor, W – verbal fluency (ability to quickly produce words), and I – inductive factor. Through subsequent research, Thurston expanded his theory of the existence of the intelligence factor by realizing that there is also a general factor of intelligence. The connection between intelligence and leadership was established already in the first forms of organizing the human community, but in a certain sense it varied with different forms of human organization and different forms of leadership that existed in those organizations, that is, historical stages.

➤ *Why is Intelligence Understood in this Way Important for Leadership?*

Research has shown that more intelligent leaders learn faster; make better assumptions, deductions, and predictions; they are better at creating a convincing vision and developing strategies that turn the vision into reality; can develop better solutions to problems; can see more within the primary and secondary implications of their decisions, and they get back on their feet faster than less intelligent leaders. With the increase in the variety of followers and the complexity of the situation, the intelligence of the leader participates to a greater extent in the overall productivity and efficiency of his leadership style, his interaction with the members of the organization (followers), that is, the organization he leads. Within the framework of certain theories, a difference is articulated between the point of view that defines intelligence as the ability to solve new problems and cope with new situations, and another point of view that understands intelligence as the ability to think abstractly, to understand the causes and consequences of a problem, the ability to distinguish the essential from the unimportant, and the ability to learn and adaptation to a given goal. Within this approach to intelligence, three basic categories of intelligence are differentiated: abstract or verbal (the ability to use concepts and terms, understanding their meaning and functionally combining them), practical intelligence (dexterity in handling objects and things and the ability to psychomotor react in problem situations), and social intelligence (interaction with people).

The psychological theory recognizes two important factors that influence the level and development of intelligence - the hereditary factor (obtained from parents through genetic material and parental intellectual support during growing up) and the environmental factor (the influence of school, society, etc.), which will be discussed in more detail in the chapter Leadership and ethics in education. In traditional psychology, intelligence is measured by the intelligence quotient (intelligence quotient) - IQ - which is a numerical expression of the development of intelligence (the real difference between mental and calendar age). For this analysis, the term intelligence quotient is not significant, but it should be said that it does not matter whether we use the term intelligence or intelligence quotient. From the multitude of theories known so far about the relationship between intelligence and leadership, in this analysis, Sternberg's triple theory of intelligence will need to be emphasized and considered, due to its comprehensiveness, persuasiveness, and applicability. This triple theory focuses on the leader's activity when solving complex mental problems. According to this theory, there are three fundamental types of intelligence - analytical intelligence, practical intelligence, and creative intelligence. Analytical intelligence represents the general ability to solve problems and can be assessed using standardized tests of mental abilities. Leaders and followers with a higher level of analytical intelligence are usually better students, they can more easily see connections between questions, and have the ability to make more precise deductions, assumptions, etc. Practical intelligence or "street wisdom" is contained in the

ability to adapt to a new situation, shape it or make a choice to fulfill one's needs.

Some aspects of practical intelligence can be very important for leadership. First, with this kind of intelligence, knowledge and experience are more important than analytical intelligence. Secondly, practical intelligence is related to certain specialties (a good pharmaceutical researcher can use his knowledge and experience to a minimal extent in collecting funds for a non-governmental organization - practical intelligence helps leaders in familiar situations and analytical intelligence in new situations). Third, modern organizations are looking for leaders and followers who have the necessary knowledge and skills to succeed and the ability to learn. Fourth, sometimes a higher level of practical intelligence can compensate for a lower level of analytical intelligence. But leaders with a higher level of analytical intelligence, all other parameters being equal, can develop their street smarts faster than leaders with a lower level of analytical intelligence. Creative intelligence, as the third component of the triple theory of intelligence, represents the ability to create unusual and useful products. Creative intelligence is related to analytical, but not legally and perfectly - a certain level of analytical intelligence is needed for creativity, but a high level of analytical intelligence does not guarantee the creativity of a leader. Similar to practical intelligence, creativity is tied to a particular specialty or subspecialty.

V. EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE – DEFINITION AND IMPORTANCE

The conventional understanding of intelligence has been significantly supplemented and changed over the past few decades, both on a general level and especially in the interaction of leadership and intelligence. Namely, in the traditional understanding of terms, "being smart" mostly meant having a high degree of intelligence, IQ (Intelligence Quotient). Modern psychological and psychological and social sciences do not associate the degree of personal satisfaction and social success with rational but rather with emotional intelligence, EQ (Emotional Quotient) - that is, with the individual's ability to empathize with others, make quality social assessments, create good relationships and be socially desirable. Emotional intelligence is also seen as "a group of mental abilities that help people recognize their feelings and the feelings of others." Aberman (2000) defines emotional intelligence as "the degree of concordance of thought, feeling, and action". Emotional intelligence also results in other emotional skills that result in the ability to integrate an individual into the social environment, which makes him successful, that is, useful, both for himself and for the environment. This dimension of intelligence is extremely important for leadership and will therefore be discussed in more detail, especially in the context of the fact that in a world of radical, rapid, and often unpredictable changes, it is very important to have qualities that enable adaptive leadership. Research in the last few decades clearly shows that EQ is much more important than IQ in many life situations, especially in leadership. Self-awareness, self-motivation, and the ability to establish a resonant

relationship with others prove extremely important in social communication, i.e. in interaction with co-workers, from compassion to the most concrete practical coordination in a multitude of daily challenges and situations.

American professor Daniel Goleman, two decades ago, warned: "Whether a company will be agile enough to survive the surprises of tomorrow largely depends on whether its leaders - especially the top management - can manage in the conditions of drastic changes own emotions". The need for mentally mobile and stimulating leaders, whose importance in a time of rapid transition and deep changes is becoming more and more emphasized, led to the sudden development of the study of leaders and leadership from the point of view of social psychology, sociology, economics, anthropology, and other humanistic disciplines. These researches led to the concept of an emotionally intelligent leader, who manages well in new situations and who is calm and irrational even in critical situations. This kind of leader does not wait for the beginning of a crisis to react. He foresees the coming changes, anticipates the future with his vision, and readily accepts new circumstances. There are at least four significant definitions of emotional intelligence. Psychologists Peter Salovey and Mayer (1990) defined it as a group of mental abilities that help people to know their own and others' feelings: Bar-On (1996) believed that it was another way to measure human effectiveness and defined it as a set of 15 abilities that are needed to deal with daily situations and navigate the world. Aberman (2000) defined emotional intelligence as the degree of connection between thoughts, feelings, and actions. Goleman (1988) expanded the previous definitions and claimed that success in life is more based on one's self-motivation, persistence in the face of frustration, mood management, adaptability, and the ability to empathize and relate to others than on one's analytical intelligence or IQ.

VI. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMOTIONS AND REASON

Due to the importance that emotional intelligence has for every person, and especially for leaders, it is worth dealing with its essence in a little more detail, more fully understanding its context and interaction with other human abilities and properties, to know it better and use it more fully. Discussing the relationship between feeling and reason, Travis Bradberry and Jean Graves explain that our sensory sensations enter the brain in a place located in the back, near the spinal cord, while complex, rational thinking takes place in the opposite, front, side of the brain. Bradberry and Greaves further explain: "When electrical signals enter our brain, they have to travel from one end of the brain to the other before a single logical thought about an event appears in our mind. This chasm in our mind that separates the entrance for the senses from the reason is a problem, because between the two is the limbic system. It is about the brain region where emotions are experienced. Thus, the two regions of the brain continuously communicate with each other through the limbic system, creating a tone through communication, a physical source of emotional intelligence, that is, the front part of the brain

judges feelings and regulates them accordingly.

VII. CHARACTERISTICS OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

Although psychology still adheres to the traditional concept of intelligence, the affective dimension of personality, emotional endowment and emotional intelligence are increasingly present within its framework.

Emotional intelligence, in essence, represents successful control, especially of harmful emotions. This ability is not genetically determined. It can develop and strengthen throughout life.

A. *The Structure of Emotional Intelligence Consists of Four Domains:*

- Self-awareness
- Social awareness
- Self-management
- Managing others

Each of these domains has multiple characteristics, and emotional intelligence has a total of eighteen characteristics. The emotional and rational minds are not incompatible but compatible abilities. For a person to be happy, and to work well and successfully, he must achieve a balance of logic, mind, and heart. Today's children spend a significant part of their time at the computer, have an increasing IQ (higher intelligence quotient compared to their parents), and neglect the development of emotional intelligence, so they are impulsive, anxious, neurotic, and antisocial.

VIII. RESONANT AND DISSONANT LEADERS

The degree of possession and ability to use emotional intelligence very significantly determines the success of a leader, especially in difficult situations. Successful and dynamic leaders find ways to manage their own and others' emotions. If the leader conveys optimism and enthusiasm with his vision and attitude to the members of his group, encourages positive emotions, and creates an emotional resonance in the members of his group, then he is a resonant leader.

If he does not reach a harmonized "wavelength" with the members of his group, does not connect with them in the right way, and causes toxic, harmful emotions in them, then we are talking about a dissonant leader, and his group acts ineffectively and disorganized. This understanding of the characteristics of successful leaders is largely based on classical empirical research. Harvard professor David McClelland has called for a revolution in assessing employee characteristics that determine success at work. He insisted on measuring competence and not intelligence, ignoring the dogma that pure intelligence is the most important for success in any activity. Thus, in this context, leadership is defined as a distinct social influence that a prominent group member (leader) has on the beliefs, opinions, emotions, and behavior of other group members,

which he motivates and directs towards the fulfillment of common goals.

The quality of superior leaders is that they are more democratic, more compassionate, more polite, more loyal, and more willing to help. Perfect leaders are parental, which means they can enjoy the development and self-actualization of other people. Such leaders, at the same time, must be able to bear being unloved, unpopular, ridiculed, and attacked, and able to recognize the objective demands of the situation and respond to them. Goleman observes: "Great leaders encourage us. They ignite passion and bring out the best in us. When we try to explain why they are so successful, we talk about strategy, vision, or powerful ideas. However, the essence is in something much more primal - great leaders move emotions".

Emotions and emotional intelligence are considered in many other areas of human activity outside of leadership. Dominik Mojsi, considering the interrelationship of globalization, geopolitics, and emotions, noticed; "My advocacy for the analysis of emotions in the geopolitical arena is based on the following: emotions are important. They influence the attitudes of people, the relations between cultures, and the behavior of nations. No one can ignore emotions: neither political leaders, history scholars, nor ordinary people. Trying to formulate the emotional patterns of our world may be dangerous, but pretending these patterns don't exist would be even more dangerous."

IX. CONCLUSION

Although the assets of an organization were considered exclusively what it owns (in the form of tangible assets or capital), more and more attention is being paid to human resources. Employees are the strength of the organization and as such need encouragement and a pleasant working environment. This is achieved by the quality leadership of a good leader, who directs the group towards the pipes of the organization in which it operates.

A leader, along with qualities such as persistence, stability, dedication to work, ambition, and the like, must also possess a high degree of emotional intelligence. By developing it, the leader strengthens his independence and self-esteem and can listen and focus on others in the environment. Good relations within the organization, along with other components, are manifested through understanding one's own and other people's emotions. To achieve this, the leader must strengthen his empathy and social responsibility.

Research has proven that it is possible to increase the level of emotional intelligence through various workshops and seminars and that by investing in it, a person becomes more competent to lead a group of people following the needs of the organization. There is an increasing number of workshops and courses where those interested are taught how to develop the qualities necessary for good leadership. Various guidelines enable people who, in addition to strengthening logical intelligence, want to strengthen this

second, already mentioned, emotional intelligence.

In the new way of doing business, where strong emphasis is placed on teams and not on individuals, the relationship between employees and their supervisors is important. Employees, feeling comfortable in their work environment, become more productive in their work. Also, they respect and follow the leader, and treat their work following his instructions. It can be said that emotional intelligence is indirectly related to the financial success of the organization itself and that it is desirable to develop it and give it the same attention as other types of intelligence.

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